

Found: Fe, 15.09; SO₄, 25.83; N, 5.28 and H₂O, 10.09; while C₂₀H₂₂ClN₃O.(FeSO₄)₂.4H₂O requires: Fe, 15.27; SO₄, 26.26; N, 5.74 and H₂O, 9.84.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titration results clearly indicate that camoquin forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with ferrous sulphate; while Fig. 1 indicates that only one complex is formed. The spectrophotometric studies by (i) Job's method, (ii) Mole ratio method and (iii) Slope ratio method also indicate that the complexation takes place in the ratio 1:2. The analytical data agree with the composition C₂₀H₂₂ClN₃O.(FeSO₄)₂.4H₂O.

Fig. 1

The stability constants calculated by Job's and Yoe and Jones' method are 7.85 and 7.98 respectively. The free energy change ΔF has been calculated by the expression $\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K$. The results are -10.81 and -11.06 K cal mole⁻¹ respectively.

The I.R. spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 237 spectrophotometer using KBr disc. Metal-nitrogen and

metal-oxygen absorption bands were observed at 655 and 680 cm⁻¹ respectively, while no such absorption bands were present in the ligand. Bonded sulphate shows strong absorption band at 1205 cm⁻¹. Band at 815 cm⁻¹ and 1655 cm⁻¹ indicate that co-ordinated water molecules are present in the complex. NH bending 1110 cm⁻¹, weak in parent compound becomes intense or modified to 1120 cm⁻¹ on complexation indicating metal-NH co-ordination. C-N stretching vibrations of aromatic secondary amine is modified from 1260 to 1270 cm⁻¹ on complexation; while C=N stretching vibration of ligand is modified from 1630 (weak) to 1640 (strong) on complexation. NH stretching of secondary aryl amine increases on complex formation from 3230 to 3340 cm⁻¹.

It may be mentioned that I. R. spectra of the complex show characteristic absorption bands of phenolic OH group namely 1010, 1205 and 1355 cm⁻¹. No unambiguous conclusion is possible regarding the structure of the complex.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Principal of the Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal for providing the necessary facilities and to U.G.C. for financial support.

References

1. S. S. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1974, **51**, 649.
2. S. S. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 642.
3. S. S. GUPTA, S. SIDDIQUI and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 769.
4. S. S. GUPTA, S. SIDDIQUI and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 242.
5. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437; 1942, **64**, 6330.
6. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **10**, 113; 1936, **10**, 97.
7. J. H. YOE and H. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
8. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.

Studies on Complexes of Metal(II) Carboxylates with Donor Molecules: Part I. Complexes of Copper(II) Alkanoates with Aromatic Amine N-oxides and Triphenylphosphine Oxide

N. KUMAR, P. L. KACHROO and R. KANT

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 001, India

Manuscript received 15 September 1978, revised 23 August 1979, accepted 19 November 1979

COPPER(II) carboxylates and their complexes with nitrogen donors have been intensively investigated because of their interesting structures and anti-ferromagnetic properties^{1,2}. However, there is no

work done on the complexes of copper(II) alkanoates with aromatic amine N-oxides and related oxygen donors except some reports on the complexes of these ligands with copper(II) acetate³⁻⁶. We now report the preparation and characterisation of complexes of pyridine N-oxide (PNO), 3-methylpyridine N-oxide (3-MePNO), quinoline N-oxide (QNO) and triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO) with copper(II) derivatives of propionic and *n*-butyric acids.

Experimental

Materials : Copper(II) propionate and *n*-butyrate were prepared by the standard method⁷. Their purity was established by metal analysis. PNO, 3-MePNO and TPPO were obtained commercially, while QNO was prepared by Ochiai's method⁸. The amine N-oxides were purified by vacuum distillation. Anhydrous TPPO was obtained by heating its hemihydrate at 110° for 3 hr and then by recrystallising from dry acetone.

Preparation of the Complexes : The complexes were prepared by the direct addition of the respective ligands to an acetone solution of copper(II) propionate or *n*-butyrate in 1 : 1 molar ratio. A representative preparation is given below :

Bis(propionato)pyridine N-oxide copper(II) : A solution of 0.62 g (0.0065 M) of PNO in acetone was mixed with a solution of 1.26 g (0.006 M) of copper(II) propionate in acetone (100 ml). The reaction mixture was concentrated under distillation to a volume of ~30 ml and filtered while hot. The filtrate, on standing overnight, deposited a crystalline solid which was separated, washed and then dried over phosphorus(V) oxide to yield 1.05 g of

the required product. The analytical data of the complexes are listed in Table 1.

Analyses and Physical Studies : Copper was estimated gravimetrically as bis(pyridine)dithiocyanatocopper(II). Carbon and hydrogen were determined in the microanalytical laboratory of the department. Molar conductance of the complexes was determined on their millimolar solutions in methanol and nitrobenzene. Molecular weights were found by cryoscopic method in nitrobenzene. Magnetic measurements were made on powdered samples by Gouy's method. Electronic spectra of the complexes were scanned on Beckman DK-2A and Carl Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometers. Infrared spectra were recorded as nujol mulls on Perkin-Elmer-621 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses indicate that the complexes are of 1 : 1 stoichiometry and may be formulated as [Cu(O₂CR)₂.L]. The low molar conductance values of the complexes reveal them to be non-ionic in nature. The molecular weights of the complexes are consistent with their dimeric molecular formula weights. The magnetic moments of the complexes fall in the range 1.37-1.51 B.M. at room temperature, and are similar to those reported for dimeric addition complexes of copper(II) acetate with oxygen donors^{5,6}. This suggests that the complexes have a dimeric, carboxylate bridged structure and involve some spin exchange between the two copper centres in each molecule.

The electronic spectra of the complexes in benzene exhibit two bands (I and II) in the regions

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, CONDUCTANCE, MOLECULAR WEIGHT, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Complex (colour) yield%	Analysis%			Molar conductance	Molecular Weight Found (Calcd.)*	Magnetic moment B.M. (Temp.°K)	Electronic Spectral Data (cm ⁻¹)	
	Found Cu	(calculated) C	(calculated) H				Band I	Band II
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇) ₂ (C ₅ H ₅ NO)] ₂ (green) 57	20.81 (20.86)	43.35 (43.34)	4.85 (4.93)	25.60 ^m 0.051 ^{nb}	675 (609)	—	14,750 ^m 14,125 ^b	— 26,315
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇) ₂ (3-CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ NO)] ₂ (green) 56	19.78 (19.95)	45.05 (45.21)	5.30 (5.34)	24.22 ^m —	— (637)	1.37 (292.5)	14,770 ^m —	— —
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇) ₂ (C ₉ H ₇ NO)] ₂ (yellow green) 58	17.93 (17.92)	51.00 (50.77)	4.55 (4.79)	36.82 ^m 0.069 ^{nb}	676 (709)	1.38 (288.0)	14,410 ^m 14,045 ^b 14,660 ^{dts}	— 25,840 26,245
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇) ₂ (C ₆ H ₅) ₂ PO] ₂ (light green) 53	12.96 (13.03)	59.20 (59.07)	5.40 (5.13)	35.67 ^m 0.043 ^{nb}	1095 (975)	1.49 (288.0)	14,535 ^m 13,990 ^b	— 25,775
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇ - <i>n</i>) ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ NO)] ₂ (green) 60	19.19 (19.11)	46.70 (46.91)	6.25 (5.71)	26.40 ^m 0.057 ^{nb}	671 (665)	1.40 (292.5)	14,390 ^m 14,165 ^b	— 26,525
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇ - <i>n</i>) ₂ (3-CH ₃ C ₅ H ₄ NO)] ₂ (green) 59	18.03 (18.34)	48.15 (48.48)	6.45 (6.06)	23.32 ^m —	— (693)	1.38 (293.0)	14,340 ^m —	— —
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇ - <i>n</i>) ₂ (C ₆ H ₇ NO)] ₂ (yellow green) 56	16.47 (16.61)	53.15 (53.33)	6.00 (5.49)	31.84 ^m 0.074 ^{nb}	855 (765)	1.40 (288.5)	14,410 ^m 14,470 ^b 14,620 ^{dts}	— 25,640 25,975
[Cu(O ₂ CC ₃ H ₇ - <i>n</i>) ₂ (C ₆ H ₅) ₂ PO] ₂ (light green) 58	12.16 (12.32)	60.45 (60.52)	6.05 (5.63)	29.30 ^m 0.051 ^{nb}	1067 (1031)	1.51 (289.0)	14,430 ^m 14,285 ^b	— 25,975

* Calculated for dimeric formula.

m=methanol; nb=nitrobenzene; b=benzene; dts=diffuse transmittance spectra.

13,990-14,450 and 25,640-26,525 cm^{-1} respectively. Band I, which appears, as a single broad band with a tail extending far into the near infrared region, is considered to originate from the copper(II) ion in a distorted octahedral environment and is assigned to $d_{xz}, \overrightarrow{d_{x^2-y^2}}$ transition⁸. Band

II, however, appears as a shoulder on the lower energy side of the charge transfer band ($\text{O} \rightarrow \text{Cu}$) occurring in the ultraviolet region and provides conclusive evidence in support of the proposed binuclear structure. The band is assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition^{5,9}. The electronic spectra of the complexes recorded in methanol show only band I. This obviously arises from the conversion of the dimeric complexes into monomeric species as a result of solvent co-ordination. The diffuse transmittance spectra of QNO complexes reveal little difference from those taken in benzene solution, suggesting thereby that these complexes have identical structure both in benzene solution and solid state.

The N-O stretching vibrations occurring at 1250 and 1278 cm^{-1} in PNO and 3-MePNO and the P=O stretching vibration occurring at 1189 cm^{-1} in TPPO undergo a negative shift of 17-30 and 8-9 cm^{-1} respectively in their complexes indicating that these ligands are co-ordinated to copper(II) through their respective oxygen atoms. In QNO complexes, however, the $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ is observed either at the same frequency (1232 cm^{-1}) as in the free ligand or is slightly shifted to higher wave numbers. This behaviour is typical of QNO-metal complexes and can be attributed to predominant $d_{\pi}-p_{\pi}$ back bonding from the metal to the ligand. However, $\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$ shows large positive shifts confirming the co-ordination of QNO to copper(II) through its N-O oxygen. The asymmetric and symmetric carboxyl stretching frequencies appear as sharp and intense peaks in the regions 1626-1519 and 1432-1416 cm^{-1} respectively. The position, nature and separation ($\sim 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of these bands are characteristically similar to those of various 1:1 binuclear addition complexes of copper(II) acetate with oxygen donors⁵. All these investigations suggest that the complexes are binuclear carboxylate bridged species similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere thanks to Professor R. K. Dewan, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Jammu, Jammu and Professor O. P. Vig, Head, Chemistry Department, Panjab University, Chandigarh for providing laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to R. K.

References

1. R. W. JOTHAM, S. F. A. KETTLE and J. A. MARKS, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 428.

2. R. J. DORDENS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **21**, 209.
3. D. M. L. GOODGAME and F. A. COTTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2298.
4. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS, E. KOKOT, S. L. LENZER, T. N. LOCKYER and E. SINN, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 2403.
5. D. H. HIBDON and J. H. NELSON, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 629.
6. J. J. MCDUGALL, L. C. NATHAN and J. H. NELSON, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **17**, 243.
7. R. L. MARTIN and H. WATERMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2545.
8. E. OCHIAI and SAI ZAI-REN, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1945, **65**, 75; *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, **45**, 8526.
9. L. DUBICKI and R. L. MARTIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 2203.
10. J. N. VAN NIEKERK and F. R. L. SCHORNING, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1953 **6**, 227; *Nature*, 1953, **171**, 36.

Syntheses of New Cobalt(III) Heterochelates Containing Three Different Bidentate Ligands in the Same Co-ordination Zone

A. SYAMAL* and P. K. MANDAL

Department of Applied Sciences and Humanities, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119 and Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 4 April 1979, revised 21 August 1979
accepted 19 November 1979

ALTHOUGH there has been considerable research interest in the syntheses and optical properties of cobalt(III) heterochelates of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})_2(\text{BB})_2]^{n+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{BB})(\text{AA})_2]^{n+}$ (where $\text{AA} \neq \text{BB}$ = bidentate ligand) containing two different bidentate ligands in the co-ordination zone¹, very little is known about the cobalt(III) heterochelates of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{BB})(\text{CC})]^{n+}$ (where $\text{AA} \neq \text{BB} \neq \text{CC}$ = bidentate ligand) containing three different bidentate ligands in the co-ordination zone. Only the complexes viz. $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{tn})(\text{tetramethylenediamine})]^{3+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{tn})(\text{neopentanediamine})]^{3+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{en})(\text{oxalate})(\text{glycine})]$ (where en = ethylenediamine and tn = trimethylenediamine) have been reported so far^{2,3}. The syntheses of such heterochelates containing three different bidentate ligands are of interest due to the following reasons:

(a) The stability of the M-L bonding in the heterochelates may be favoured in comparison to that in the homochelates, (b) the chromophore system is amenable to variation, (c) novel magnetic and spectral properties may develop due to the variation in the ligand field strength, (d) novel distortion may be noticed, (e) the charge of the complex cation can be varied by proper choice of ligands, (f) the heterochelates may serve as models for the naturally occurring metal-ternary or

* Author to whom all correspondence should be directed.